

PAM 43.689 frag. 33 (IAA Plate 90 frags. 86-88) Identified as a 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) fragment (Gen 32:29-30?)

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PAM 43.689 is one of the many photographs of plates with Qumran Cave 4 fragments which had not yet been identified by 1960. One of the fragments on this plate, fourth row, fifth from the right, numbered frag. 33 in DJD 33, plate XXVIII, was placed upside down on the plate. The editors of PAM 43.689 noted that this fragment was no longer located on Mus. Inv. 90, but also mentioned:

Three small illegible fragments not appearing on the PAM photograph of Mus. Inv. 90 have been placed below frags. 80-82 on the museum plate (DJD 33, p. 213).

In fact, these three fragments are the same frag. 33 but broken into three pieces. Compare the images of PAM 43.689 and those of IAA Plate 90 (joined together with Gimp):

The hand of the writing (so-called early Hasmonaean) corresponds closely to that of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a; published in DJD 12). On the IAA color photographs the three pieces of the fragment seem to have a red-brown color similar to that of 4Q1. The textual remains of lines 2 and 3 are fairly certain (read after *את waw* or perhaps *yod*).

]וכל[2
] אתו] 3

This text might fit with Gen 32:29-30 (ותוכל) followed by (יברך אתו) or Gen 37:35 (וכל) followed by (ויברך אתו). In both cases the lines can be restored on the basis of the Masoretic or Samaritan text resulting in lines of the same length as in 4Q1. The word-dividing space between ך and אתו in line

3 is small, which is uncommon for 4Q1. The broken remains of line 1 are more difficult to read and to match with the text of Genesis. I propose to read the first letter as the bottom left part of *lamed* or *ayin*, followed by, a downstroke of, for example, *waw*. If one tries to match these traces with the other ones which fit Gen 32:29-30 or Gen 37:35, then one might read here לא or perhaps לו (if one reads with the LXX εἶπεν δὲ αὐτῷ Οὐ).

The fragment might then be transcribed as follows:

לא אשלחך כי אם ברכתני ויאמר אליו מה שמך ויאמר יעקב ויאמר לא	1
יעקב יאמר עוד שמך כי אם ישראל כי שרית עם אלהים ועם אנשים ותוכל	2
וישאל יעקב ויאמר הגידה נא שמך ויאמר למה זה תשאל לשמי ויברך אתו	3

The fragment cannot be joined to any of the identified or unidentified fragments published as 4Q1, and the textual identification with Gen 32:29-30 is therefore plausible but not certain.

References:

- DJD 12 Eugene Ulrich, Frank Moore Cross, et al., eds., *Qumran Cave 4, VI: Genesis to Numbers*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XII (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1994)
- DJD 33 Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XXXIII (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001)

Screen captures from:

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285464>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-503086>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-503092>

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